

THE TIKTOK-IFICATION OF MENTAL HEALTH

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Topic: Mental Health

Title: The TikTok-ification Of Mental Health

Objectives: To investigate the credibility of TikTok's mental health content relating to ADHD and Depression using a rubric.

Background: Tiktok's platform allows the display of a multitude of mental health content, including disorders like ADHD and depression. Consequently, teenagers who feel like they have been suffering from specific symptoms have begun to self-diagnose themselves with said disorders. While other studies may have researched how accurate mental health resources on social media are, this study aims to analyze the TikTok videos using a clear, crafted rubric to investigate the trustworthiness of mental health advice shown to adolescents.

Methods: By creating a rubric to evaluate 5 TikTok videos, specifically talking about self diagnosed ADHD and depression, we determined the video's possible motives or influences based on 5 criteria: references from professionals, specific language that does not encourage self-diagnosis/relatability, credibility of the creator, correct medical information, and whether or not professional medical help is urged. These criteria were measured as "present" or "not present", determining whether the content is credible or not.

Results: After all 4 TikTok videos were analyzed by study participants, it was found that TikTok 2 was the only video that had all the criteria present with 83.3%. Throughout all media, the most commonly met criterion was "correct medical information," while the least prevalent was "professional references." TikTok 4 had the least amount of criteria present, with a score of 33.3%.

Conclusions: The data collected depicts that only one Tiktok video, Tiktok 2 met every criteria with an overall 83.3%. In contrast, the rest of the videos were below 60%, with one being 33.3%. This emphasizes that the mental health TikToks are not sufficient enough to diagnose a person solely, meaning a person will not know if they have ADHD or depression unless actually diagnosed by a professional. To study the deeper implications of the misinforming videos, a survey of teens that have been interacting with this content should be conducted for a better overview.

Keyword 1: Tiktok

Keyword 2: Self-Diagnosis

Keyword 3: Mental-Health

Keyword 4: Content Analysis

1. **I confirm that the abstract and that all information is correct:** Yes
2. **I confirm that the abstract constitutes consent to publication:** Yes
3. **I confirm that I submit this abstract on behalf of all authors:** Yes